

A Preliminary Survey of Traditional Organic Piscicides from Local Flora of Paschim Medinipur District, West Bengal, India

Dr. Dulal Kumar De¹, Dr. Ramaprasad Bhattacharya², Sreyashri Giri³, Bratati Bhanja⁴

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Botany, Midnapore College (Autonomous), Midnapore, West Bengal, India

²JDPI, Bikash Bhavan, Kolkata, India

^{3,4}Research Scholar, Midnapore College (Autonomous), Midnapore, West Bengal, India

ABSTRACT

The present work is an extensive field work in different Blocks of Paschim Medinipur district and review of published literature concerning piscicidal properties of locally available plants growing in this district. It will provide comprehensive information for further research. Due to presence of safe phyto-chemical, these plants would be an eco-friendly alternative of synthetic chemical substances to reduce the chemical hazards in the environment. The present study provides only preliminary report and may be the source for further scientific and analytical research to evaluate the efficacy of the toxic as well as safe properties of these plants. Total 90 no. of plant species belonging to 81 no of Genus, 46 no of Families are enumerated alphabetically with scientific names, common Names, ecological status, parts used and chemical nature. Traditional plant piscicides used by tribes in this district has also been studied. No such work has yet been done in this district.

KEYWORDS: Herbal Piscicides, Traditional plant piscicide, Paschim Medinipur District, West Bengal

INTRODUCTION

A piscicide is a chemical substance, which stupefy and or poison the fish. Though traps and nets are important tools used for capture fishes from rivers and streams but use of various plants as fish poison (called Herbal piscicide) is also a very old practice in the history. The main objective of this work is to provide information of unknown or less known Piscicidal plant taxa and their botanical identities in the district of Paschim Medinipur and to give information about the effects of these herbal fish toxins to human beings and other carnivores. It would be important to have an awareness regarding the poisonous plants which, when used in the proper, prescribed dose, for stupefying fishes and would be ready information to the fishermen for fish farming and parts used as piscicide. This data will help Botanist, Ethno-Botanists, Fishermen, Biochemists and Scientists of other allied disciplines for their research programme. Herbal piscicides are also the

best eco- friendly alternative of unsafe chemical pesticide in aquaculture to control fish fry predators and unwanted fishes from aquaculture ponds. These are valuable one due to the properties of eco -friendly, ease of availability, high efficiency, less toxicity to non-targeted animals and rapid biodegradability (Yunis Aj *et al*, 2014). Plant parts of different Piscicidal plants can be applied directly in the form of aqueous extract or extract dissolved in alcohol (Ekpendu EA, *et al.*, 2014). In some cases dried plant products are applied after soaking in water overnight as piscicidal. Generally plant extracts are called botanicals but when toxic to fish called Piscicide (Fafioye OO, 2005). Indigenous people of all over the world use various fish poisons to kill or stupefy the fishes (Jeremy So.2002). In India, most rural communities depend on the wild resources to meet their food needs during food crisis period and also use as additional food supplements (Jawale CS, 2018).

How to cite this paper: Dr. Dulal Kumar De | Dr. Ramaprasad Bhattacharya | Sreyashri Giri | Bratati Bhanja "A Preliminary Survey of Traditional Organic Piscicides from Local Flora of Paschim Medinipur District, West Bengal, India" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-7 | Issue-1, February 2023, pp.822-844, URL: www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd52759.pdf

Copyright © 2023 by author (s) and International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development Journal. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY 4.0) (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>)

Since ancient periods Tribal people used to use various plant products for fish poisoning (Murthy EN *et al.*, 2010). Though at present some unhealthy chemicals are used for this purpose, but still tribals are using this easy and simple method for fishing in remote areas (Kumar V. *et al.*, 2003). Many research works are going on for documenting many fish toxins and their use (Sharma S.K 1997). So far literature surveyed, no such information about piscicidal plants has yet been published. The tribal communities in this district are Santal, Lodha (Sabar), Munda, Oraon, Bhumijis and Kherias. Besides agriculture, hunting and the collection of forest products, fishing is an alternative source of food for Tribes in this district. They not only collect fish for food but also earn money by selling them in daily markets. During field survey, it has been noted that Tribal of this district use indigenous knowledge by using plant products available surround the areas for fish stupefying and fish killing purpose and poisoning is generally done in stagnant pools or slow flowing streams and rivers which allow the pounded part of plant to concentrate without being washed away or diluted by current. Sometimes streams are partly blocked to slow down the flow of water. During the survey period, five no. plant species like *Persicaria orientalis* (L.) Spach, *Euphorbia antiquorum* L., *Euphorbia nerrifolia* L., *Acacia auriculiformis* A.Cunn ex Benth., *Croton banplandianum* Baill. have been identified which are traditionally used by the Tribes in this district as fish toxin. Among these five plant species, *Persicaria orientalis* L and *Acacia auriculiformis* A. Cunn ex Benth. are used profusely by the tribes. During conversation with the Ethnic people, it has also been noted that now- a- days they are very much interested to use the chemical piscicide rather herbal one due to unavailability of some plants and quick action of chemical piscicide. Many fishermen of this district are generally using unhealthy chemicals like agriculturally used pesticides in pond for fish poisoning. Piscicidal plants products actually stupefy the fishes without killing the whole fish stock when these are used in limited dose in limited time (Kamal kishor HN, *et al.* 2009). Biochemical compounds present in piscicidal plants stun the fishes when it passes through its gills or ingested directly. The fishes come to the surface because of lack of dissolved oxygen and during this period fishes exhibit abnormal behaviours due to asphyxia, haemorrhages in internal organs or nervous breakdown. (Das SK, *et al.* 2018, Murthy EN *et al.*, 2010). Generally Saponin and Rotenone containing plants are used for this purpose. Chopra *et al.* reported 112 species of plants having piscicidal action from different states of India. (Chopra RN, *et al.* 1958) and 90 no. of plants have

been identified as piscicidal plants in Paschim Medinipur District, West Bengal. Several plants belonging to different families, having a number of compounds (Saponins; tannins, alkaloids, steroids, alkenylphenols; di and tri terpenoids; and others) with high pesticidal activity are used to control predatory fish; disease causing insects such as mosquito larvae and harmful fresh water snails (Tiwari S., *et al.* 2003). It has been proved that saponin and rotenone are not harmful to human beings if they are used scientifically. The plant products degrade easily within 7-12 days and are considered environment friendly as they act as manures following biodegradation (Chakroff M. 1976). But when chemicals like agriculture pesticides are used for this purpose, it creates health hazards. Poisoning is generally done in stagnant pools or slow flowing streams and rivers which allow the pounded part of plant to concentrate without being washed away or diluted by current. Sometimes streams are partly blocked to slow down the flow of water. Most ichthiotoxic plant poisons initially works as stupefying or paralysing agent and later lead to death of the fish. Piscicidal plants used in fishing actually stupefy the fishes without killing the whole fish stock (Dalela, R.C. *et al.*, 1978). Saponin is one of the group of glucosides found in many plant species with known foaming properties when mixed with water Saponins, toxins normally break down in the digestive system and enter the bloodstream. Fishes take in saponins directly into their blood stream through their gills. The toxins act on the respiratory organs of the fish. Saponins also cause the breakdown of red blood cells that help the toxin to spread quickly. Fishes that are washed away into fresh water revive and can return to their pre-toxic condition. Because of this, the fisherman would have to gather the stunned fish quickly as they floated to the surface. Neuwinger postulated that saponins permeabilize the gill epithelial cells of fish allowing essential electrolytes to escape (Neuwinger, H. D. 1994). Plants containing rotenones are the second utilized fish poison. Rotenone is an alkaloid toxin, in a group called flavonoids and stuns fish by impairing their oxygen consumption. Vickery and Vickery claims that saponins are generally only toxic to cold-blooded animals (Vickery, M.L. *et al.* 1981) and saponins may offer an attractive alternative for Rotenone in fish management projects since the latter is somewhat toxic to small mammals. Relatively little is known about how most fish poisons work on a molecular level, with the possible exception of rotenone. Rotenone is known to inhibit NADH-Q reductase in the mitochondrial electron transport chain (Stryer, L., 1995), and this prevents the mitochondria from using

NADH as a substrate. Electron transfer is virtually halted, and the organism cannot produce enough ATP, which leads to asphyxia and paralysis, followed by death (Neuwinger, H.D, 1994). Although rotenone is known to be toxic to nearly all animals, but it decays in Sunlight and in air (Merck Index, 1989), so do not cause much harm to mammals and other non-target species. When rotenone is used to treat large reservoirs, the treatment is carried out at times of low water, and out flow from the reservoir is cut off so that the rivers or waterways are not poisoned. According to literatures surveyed (Bhattacharya, S, (1976-93); Kirtikar, K. R *et al.*,1935; Chopra, R.N *et al.*, 1956; Chopra, R.N., *et al.* 1969; Chatterjee, A., *et al.*1991-2001; Pal, D.C. *et al.*1998; Negi, S.S. *et al.* 2007) these Piscicidal plants have immense medicinal values.

Methodology: During the survey period, from June, 2019 to May, 2020, extensive field studies were carried out in more tribal reach areas of this district. For betterment regular field visits were carried out in the study area. Selection of area was based on tribal population or tribal richness. Near about twenty blocks of this district have been covered for this survey work. Data were collected on seasonal basis, i.e. pre monsoon, monsoon, post monsoon and winter during the survey period. Standard questionnaire were used. Information was collected by conversation with the knowledge providers. Plants use in fishing were collected and identified on the basis of vernacular name, regional floras and published literature (Prain, D, 1963; Bennet, S.S.R, 1987). They are enumerated alphabetically with scientific names, vernacular names, family and used parts (Table-1&2). Extensive literature survey was done to verify the name of plants and their use in fish poisoning. The methodologies described by Jain (1999), Chadwick D.J. *et al.* (1994) were adopted for this investigation. By using the standard methods (Martin, 1995) of semi structured questionnaires, interviews and participatory appraisals, collection of information from the tribes (Santals, Lodhas and Oraon) and local communities of this region was carried out. Herbarium sheets of all collected specimens have been prepared according to standard method (Jain S K, *et al.*, 1977) and preserved in the Herbarium of Dept. of Botany, Midnppore College (Autonomous), Midnapore for further study.

Study area: The District of Paschim Medinipur is located in the South- Western part of West Bengal. It is at 23 meters above Sea level. The climate of this district follows a hot tropical monsoon weather pattern. Soil types near Kangsabati River are alluvial, whereas towards Rangamati are lateritic. Vegetation

includes Species of *Eucalyptus* and Sal (*Shorea robusta* L). Forest is located on the North West side of the Midnapore Town. The average annual precipitation is 2,111mm. According to the 2011 census Paschim Medinipur district has a population of 5,943,300 (Wikipedia 2018; District Census 2011; Census 2011). Schedule Caste (SC) constitutes 19.1 % while Schedule Tribes (ST) are upto 14.9% of total population of the District. 12.2% people live in urban areas while 87.8% live in the rural areas. (Census, 2011). Fig 1,2 show the location of West Midnapore District in West Bengal & Figure 3 shows the Blocks of Paschim Medinipur District(mapsfindia,2020).

Fig- 1 West Bengal in India

Fig-2 Location of Paschim Medinipur district

Maps

Fig-3 Blocks of Paschim Medinipur district

Fig-6 *Persicaria orientalis* (L.) Spach

Fig-7 *Acacia auriculiformis* A. Cunnex Benth.

Fig-4 *Croton banplandianum* Baill.

Fig-5 *Euhorbia nerrifolia* L.

Fig-8 *Euphorbia antiquorum* L.

Results:**Table 1: List of available Piscicidal Plant in Paschim Medinipur District with their Family, Habit, Habitat, Ecological Status, Flowering and Fruiting Period and Used Parts**

Sl. No.	Scientific Name of Plants	Family	Habit	Habitat	An/B/Per	Ecological status	Fl & Fr. Period	Used Part	Reference
1.	<i>Justicia adhatoda</i> L.	Acanthaceae	S	T	Per	Common, Cultivated, Wild	Dec-Apr	Leaves	Petr T. T.(1999)
2.	<i>Alangium salvifolium</i> (L.f.) Wang.	Alangiaceae	UT	T	Per	Common, Wild	Mar-July	Root bark	Agharkar S.P.(1991)
3.	<i>Achyranthes aspera</i> L.	Amaranthaceae	H	T	An to per	Common, Wild	Sept-Apr	Whole plant	Ashraf, M. <i>et al.</i> (2010).
4.	<i>Agave sisalana</i> Perr.	Amaryllidaceae	S	T	Per	Frequent, Cultivated	Oct-Mar	Leaves	Chiotha SS <i>et al.</i> (1991)
5.	<i>Crinum asiaticum</i> (L.)		H	T	Per	Frequent, Wild	April – July	Roots, Leaves	Pedro (1990)
6.	<i>Anacardium occidentale</i> L.	Anacardiaceae	S	T	Per	Frequent, Cultivated	Dec-May	NR	Agharkar (1991), Bombay (1953)
7.	<i>Semecarpus anacardium</i> L.f.		T	T	Per	Frequent, Wild, Cultivated	June-Feb	NR	Agharkar S.P.(1991)
8.	<i>Centella asiatica</i> L.(Urb.)	Apiaceae	H	T	Per	Common, Cultivated, Wild	July – Jan	NR	Chopra R.N. <i>et al.</i> (1933)
9.	<i>Adenium obesum</i> Roem & Schett	Apocynaceae	CH	T	Per	Frequent, Cultivated	Whole year	Bark, Leaves	
10.	<i>Alstonia scholaris</i> (L.) R.Br.		UT	T	Per	Common, cultivated, Wild	Oct-Feb	Latex	Bandaru N. <i>et al.</i> , (2016)
11.	<i>Holarrhena pubescens</i> Wall. Ex G.Don.		T	T	Per	Frequent, Wild, Cultivated	Oct – Mar	Stem bark	Murthy E.N. <i>et al.</i> (2010)
12.	<i>Nerium oleander</i> L.		S	T	Per	Common, Cultivated	Feb – Oct	Leaf, Fruit, Bark	Ashraf M. <i>et al.</i> , (2010)
13.	<i>Plumeria rubra</i> L.		UT	T	Per	Frequent, Cultivated	Apr-Sept	Leaves	Dey Abhijit, <i>et al.</i> (2015).
14.	<i>Rauwolfia serpentina</i> (L.) Benth. Ex Kurz.		S	T	Per	Frequent, Wild, Cultivated	Mar – Dec	Stem, Leaves	Sinha M.K. <i>et al.</i> (2010), Pedro (1990)
15.	<i>Cascabela thevetia</i> (L.) H. Lippold		S	T	Per	Common, Cultivated	Whole year	Pericarp, stem, leaf, Bark	Envis (2017), Singh S.K. <i>et al.</i> , (2010)
16.	<i>Amorphophallus campanulatus</i> Blume. ex. Decne.		Araceae	S	T	Bi	Common, Wild, Cultivated	Apr-Dec	Corn
17.	<i>Calotropis procera</i> Aiton	Asclepiadaceae	US	T	Per	Common, Wild, Cultivated	Jan-Aug	Root, Latex	Ashraf M. <i>et al.</i> , (2010), Katewa SS. <i>et al.</i> ,(2008)
18.	<i>Yucca filamentosa</i> L.	Asparagaceae	S	T	Per	Frequent, Cultivated	Apr-June	NR	Sinha M.K. <i>et al.</i> (2010)

19.	<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i> L.	Asteraceae	H	T	Ann	Abundant, Wild	Aug-Nov	Whole Plant	Tag Hui., <i>et al.</i> (2005), Das S. <i>et al.</i> (2003)
20.	<i>Chromolaena odorata</i> (L.)R.M. King &H. Rob.		S	T	Per	Abundant, Wild	Sept-Feb	Leaves	Envis (2017), Lamba S.S. (1970),
21.	<i>Acmella oleracea</i> (L.) R.K.Jansen.		H	T	Ann	Abundant, Wild	Aug-Jan	Whole plant, leaves, twigs	Tag Hui., <i>et al.</i> (2005), Namsa Nima D, <i>et al.</i> (2011), Nimachow G. <i>et al.</i> (2008)
22.	<i>Tridax procumbens</i> L.		H	T	Ann	Abundant, Wild	Whole year	Leaves	Ambasta S.P. (2006),
23.	<i>Senna alata</i> (L.)Roxb.	Caesalpiniaceae	S	T	Per	Wild, common	Aug-Mar	Leaves	Ayyanar M. <i>et al.</i> (2010), Colonel B. <i>et al.</i> , (1955)
24.	<i>Cassia fistula</i> L.		UT	T	Per	Common, Wild	Mar – Dec	Stem bark	Sinha M.K. <i>et al.</i> (2010), Ayyanar M. <i>et al.</i> (2010)
25.	<i>Senna sophora</i> (L.) Roxb.		WH	T	Ann	Abundant, Wild	July – Dec	NR	Sinha M.K. <i>et al.</i> (2010)
26.	<i>Carica papaya</i> L.	Caricaceae	S	T	Per	Common, Cultivated	Whole year	Seed	Ayotunde E.O. <i>et al.</i> (2011)
27.	<i>Calophyllum inophyllum</i> L.	Calophyllaceae	H	T	Per	Frequent, Cultivated	Apr-Nov	NR	Colonel B. <i>et al.</i> , (1955)
28.	<i>Terminalia arjuna</i> (Roxb.) Wight & Arn.	Combretaceae	T	T	Per	Common, Cultivated	Mar – Dec	Stem bark	Joshi P. (1986)
29.	<i>Terminalia bellirica</i> (Gaertn.) Roxb.		T	T	Per	Frequent, Wild, Cultivated	Mar – Feb	Karnel, Bark	Pedro (1990), Chopra R.N. <i>et al</i> (1933)
30.	<i>Cuscuta reflexa</i> Roxb.	Convolvulaceae	CH	T	Per	Common, Wild	Nov – Mar	NR	Malla B. <i>et al.</i> (2011)
31.	<i>Ipomoea carnea</i> Jacq.		S	Aq.	Per	Common Wild	Whole year	Leaves	Hazarika R. <i>et al.</i> , (2015), Wanule D.D.(2012)
32.	<i>Costus speciosus</i> (J. Koenig) Sm.	Costaceae	H	T	Per	Frequent, Wild	June – Nov	Tuberous root stock	Heda N.K. <i>et al.</i> (2009), Kulkarni D.K. <i>et al.</i> (1990)
33.	<i>Dioscorea esculenta</i> (Lour.) Burkill	Dioscoreaceae	CH	T	Ann/Per	Frequent, Wild	Oct – Dec	NR	Malla B. <i>et al.</i> (2011)
34.	<i>Shorea robusta</i> Gaertn.	Dipterocarpaceae	T	T	Per	Common, Wild,Cultivated	Feb – July	Stem bark	Mishra R. <i>et al.</i> , (2014)
35.	<i>Diospyros melanoxylon</i>	Ebenaceae	T	T	Per	Frequent, Wild, cultivated	Mar – July	Fruit	Murthy E.N, <i>et al.</i> (2010)

	Roxb.								
36.	<i>Chrozophora rottleri</i> (Geiseler) A.Juss. ex Spreng.	Euphorbiaceae	H	T	Ann	Abundant, Wild	Feb – April	Leaves	Joshi P. (1986)
37.	<i>Euphorbia antiquorum</i> L.		S	T	Per	Frequent, Wild	Jan-July	Whole plant	Satya V. et al. (2010), Ramanayaka J.C. et al. (2006)
38.	<i>Euphorbia hirta</i> (L.)		H	T	Ann	Abundant, Wild	Feb – Dec	Latex	Yadav R.P. et al. (2013)
39.	<i>Euphorbia nerifolia</i> (L.)		U S	T	Per	Common, Wild, Cultivated	Jan-June	Whole plant, Latex	Das S. et al., (2003),
40.	<i>Euphorbia pulcherrima</i> Willd. Ex Klotzsch		S	T	Per	Frequent, Cultivated	Oct – Jan	Stem bark, Latex	Yadav R.P. et al. (2013)
41.	<i>Euphorbia tirucalli</i> L.		W S	T	Per	Infrequent, cultivated	May-Oct	Latex	Kumar A. et al., (2010), Tiwari S. et al.(2006)
42.	<i>Jatropha curcas</i> L.		S	T	Per	Frequent, wild	Mar – Oct	NR	Chopra R.N. et al. (1933)
43.	<i>Jatropha gossypifolia</i> L.		U S	T	Per	Common, Wild	Apr – Aug	Leaf, Stem, Bark	Singh D. et al. (2002)
44.	<i>Ricinus communis</i> L.		S	T	Per	Common, Wild, Cultivated	Sept-Mar	Leaves, Seeds	Ashraf M., et al. (2010), Pedro (1990)
45.	<i>Abrus precatorius</i> L.		Fabaceae	C S	T	Per	Common, wild	Oct-May	Seed
46.	<i>Acacia auriculiformis</i> Benth	T		T	Per	Common, Cultivated	Dec-Mar	Fruit	Mishra et al.(2014)
47.	<i>Albizia lebbek</i> (L.) Benth.	T		T	Per	Common, Wild, Cultivated	Mar-Dec	Bark,Leaf	Dominic R. et al.(2012)
48.	<i>Albizia procera</i> (Roxb.) Benth.	T		T	Per	Common, Cultivated, Wild	July-Aug	Leaf,Stem bark	Sinha M.K. et al.(2010), Rai P.K. et al. (2010)
49.	<i>Lathyrus sativus</i> L.	H		T	Ann	Frequent Cultivated,	Oct. - Nov.	NR	Agharkar S.P. (1991)
50.	<i>Butea monosperma</i> (Lam.) Taub.	T		T	Per	Frequent, Wild	Mar-Oct	Whole plant, Stem, Bark	Patil M. V., et al. (2006), Mishra R. et al., (2014)
51.	<i>Acacia pennata</i> (L.) Willd.	SS		T	Per	Frequent Wild	Oct-Jan	Seed	Negi KS. et al. (2009)
52.	<i>Guilandina bonduc</i> L.	CS		T	Per	Frequent, Wild.	Mar – May	Pulped fruit, stem	Chopra R.N. et al. (1933), Lamba S.S.(1970)
53.	<i>Entada scandens</i> (L.) Benth.	T		T	Per	Infrequent Wild.	Dec.-April	Seeds	Nadkarni K.M. (1996)
54.	<i>Erythrina suberosa</i> Roxb.	UT		T	Per	Frequent, Cultivated	Feb – July	Bark	Pawar S.,et al. (2004)

55.	<i>Crotalaria spp</i>		H	T	Ann	Frequent, Wild.	Oct – Dec	Leaves	Ramanayaka J.C. <i>et al.</i> (2006)
56.	<i>Mimosa pudica L.</i>		H	T	Per	Comon, Wild	Whole year	Leaves	Sinha M.K. <i>et al.</i> (2010)
57.	<i>Pongamia pinnata (L.) Pierre</i>		UT	T	Per	Frequent, Wild, Cultivated	Arpi-Dec	Root, Leaves	Ambasta S.P. (2006)
58.	<i>Pterocarpus marsupium Roxb.</i>		T	T	Per	Frequent, Wild, Cultivated	Aug-April	Bark	Heda N.K. <i>et al.</i> (2009)
59.	<i>Tamarindus indica L.</i>		T	T	Per	Common, Cultivated, Wild	April – Mar	Seed husk	Singh N.P. (1988)
60.	<i>Tephrosia purpurea (L.) Pers.</i>		S	T	Per	Abundant, Wild	Oct – Mar	Beans,Roots ,Seeds	Bhagya B. <i>et al.</i> (2009), Lamba S.S.(1970)
61.	<i>Juglans regia L</i>	Juglandaceae	T	T	Per	Infrequent, Cultivated	March-June	Bark, leaves, rind of unripe fruit	Pradhan B.K. <i>et al.</i> (2008), Negi KS. <i>et al.</i> (2009)
62.	<i>Clerodendrum infortunatum L.</i>	Lamiaceae	S	T	Annual	Frequent,Wild	Feb – July	NR	Colonel <i>et al.</i> , (1955),
63.	<i>Barringtonia acutangula (L.) Gaertn.</i>	Lecythidaceae	T	T	Per	Frequent, Wild	May-Oct	Seed,Root, Bark, Fruit	Yumnam J.Y. <i>et al.</i> (2013), Moyon W.A. <i>et al.</i> (2017)
64.	<i>Careya arborea Roxb.</i>		UT	T	Per	Frequent, Wild,	Feb-July	Root, Bark, Leaves	Tag Hui., <i>et al.</i> (2005), Heda N.K. <i>et al.</i> (2009)
65.	<i>Gloriosa superba L.</i>	Liliaceae	CH	T	Per	Infrequent, Wild	July-Dec	Leaves	Chopra R.N. <i>et al.</i> (1933)
66.	<i>Strychnos nux-vomica L.</i>	Loganiaceae	UT	T	Per	Frequent,Wild	Mar-Dec	Seeds,Fruits	Sinha M.K. <i>et al.</i> (2010), Ashraf M. <i>et al.</i> , (2010)
67.	<i>Ammannia baccifera L.</i>	Lythraceae	H	S.Aq	Annual	Common, Wild,	Sept-Dec	Whole plant	Bombay (1953), Agharkar S.P. (1991)
68.	<i>Grewia asiatica L.</i>	Malvaceae	UT	T	Per	Frequent, Wild, Cultivated	Whole year	NR	Pedro (1990)
69.	<i>Martynia annua L.</i>	Martyniaceae	H	T	Annual	Frequent, Wild	July – Aug	Leaves	Sinha M.K. <i>et al.</i> (2010)
70.	<i>Azadirachta indica A. Juss.</i>	Meliaceae	T	T	Per	Common, Wild,Cultivated,	Mar-July	NR	Malla B., <i>et al.</i> (2011)
71.	<i>Tinospora cordifolia (Willd.) Miers</i>	Menispermaceae	CH	T	Per	Common, Wild	Mar – Dec	Branches	Pedro (1990)
72.	<i>Moringa oleifera Lam.</i>	Moringaceae	UT	T	Per	Common, Cultivated,	Jan – May	Seed, Root bark	Kamble Manoj T., <i>et al.</i> (2014).
73.	<i>Olex scandens Roxb.</i>	Olacaceae	SS	T	Per	Frequent, Wild,	April-December	Leaves	Heda N.K. <i>et al.</i> (2009)
74.	<i>Ludwigia perennis L.</i>	Onagraceae	WH	S.Aq.	Per	Common, Wild	Whole year	Whole plant	Mishra Rajni., <i>et al.</i> (2014)

75.	<i>Argemone mexicana</i> L.	Papaveraceae	H	T	Annual	Common, Wild	Whole year	Bark, Leaf, Fruit	Sinha M.K. <i>et al.</i> (2010),
76.	<i>Cleistanthus collinus</i> (Roxb.) Benth.ex Hook.f.	Phyllanthaceae	UT	T	Per	Frequent, Wild	Sept-April	Young tender shoot, Fruit, Bark	Heda N.K. <i>et al.</i> (2009), Nadkarni K.M.(1996)
77.	<i>Plumbago indica</i> L.	Plumbaginaceae	S	T	Per	Frequent, Cultivated, Wild	Sept-Mar	NR	Agharkar S.P. (1991)
78.	<i>Polygonum hydropiper</i> L.	Polygonaceae	H	Aquatic	Annual	Frequent, Wild	Oct – Dec	Whole Plant	Petr T.T. (1999), Tag Hui., <i>et al.</i> (2005)
79.	<i>Persicaria orientalis</i> (L.) Spach		H	T	Per	Common, Wild	Aug-Dec	Whole Plant	Choudhary R.K. <i>et al.</i> , (2011)
80.	<i>Haldinia cordifolia</i> (Roxb.) Ridsdale	Rubiaceae	T	T	Per	Frequent, Cultivated	June-May	Bark	Murthy E.N. <i>et al.</i> (2010).
81.	<i>Randia spinosa</i> (Poir.)		S	T	Per	Frequent, Wild	April-Dec	Fruit, Unripened fruit	Nagi K.S. <i>et al.</i> (2009), Ignacimuthu S. <i>et al.</i> (2006)
82.	<i>Aegle marmelos</i> (L.) Correa	Rutaceae	T	T	Per	Common, Cultivated, Wild	May-Mar	Root bark	Envis (2017), Narasimhan P.L. <i>et al.</i> , (1991), Joshi P. (1986)
83.	<i>Sapindus mukorossi</i> Gaertn.	Sapindaceae	T	T	Per	Common, Cultivated	Apr-Dec	Fruit	Lamba S.S. (1970), Pedro (1990)
84.	<i>Schleichera oleosa</i> (Lour.) Oken		T	T	Per	Frequent, Wild,	Feb – Aug	Fruit	Joshi P. (1986),
85.	<i>Madhuca longifolia</i> (J.Konig) J.F. Macbr.	Sapotaceae	T	T	Per	Frequent, Wild, Cultivated	Dec – July	Seeds, Oil cake, Stem	Nagi K.S. <i>et al.</i> (2009), Kulkarni, D. K., <i>et al.</i> (1990)
86.	<i>Datura metel</i> L.	Solanaceae	H	T	Per	Common, Wild, Cultivated	Aug-May	Leaves	Mahajan R.T. <i>et al.</i> , (1989), Sinha M.K. <i>et al.</i> (2010)
87.	<i>Cestrum nocturnum</i> L.		H	T	Per	Frequent, Cultivated	July – Nov	Leaves	Jawale C.S., <i>et al.</i> (2012). Jawale C.S. <i>et al.</i> (2010)
88.	<i>Solanum nigrum</i> L.		H	T	Ann	Common, Wild	Whole year	Berries	Mahajan R.T. <i>et al.</i> (1989),
89.	<i>Holoptelea integrifolia</i> Planch.	Ulmaceae	T	T	Per	Frequent, Cultivated	Sept – Feb	Leaves, Stem bark	Kulkarni, D. K., <i>et al.</i> (1990), Joshi P.(1986)
90.	<i>Lantana camara</i> L.	Verbenaceae	S	T	Per	Abundant, Wild	Whole year	NR	Khare C.P. (2007)

H- Herb, S= Shrub, T= Tree, S.Aq- Semi aquatic, Aq- Aquatic, Per- Perennial, Ann- Annual, Bi- Bi annual, NR- Not Reported

Key: R-rare (less than 5 trees per 100m²); C-common (between 5-15 trees per 100m²); Abundant (above 15 trees per 100m²)

Table 2: List of Common name and Chemical Ingredients of Piscicidal Plant in Paschim Medinipur District

Sl. No	Scientific Name of Plants	Common Name		
1.	<i>Abrus precatorius</i> L.	Kuch phal, Latumoni, Ratti	Alka, Flav, Sapo	Hussain A. Zahir, <i>et al.</i> (2014).
2.	<i>Acacia auriculiformis</i> Benth	Akash moni, Australian wattle, Bengali babul	Flav, Sapo, Ster	Sharma, Nidhi, <i>et al.</i> (2017)
3.	<i>Acacia pennata</i> (L.) Willd.	Rusty mimosa, Agla bel, Biswal	Flav, Ster	Zothantluanga James H. <i>et al.</i> (2020).
4.	<i>Achyranthes aspera</i> L.	Apang, Prickly chaff flower, Puth kanda	Alk, Flav, Sapo	Srivastav Praven Kumar.(2014).
5.	<i>Acmella oleracea</i> (L.)R.K.Jansen.	Toothache plant, Akarkara, Para cress	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster, Triter	Tiwari.H.P. <i>et al</i> (1990).
6.	<i>Adenium obesum</i> Roem & Schett	Adenium, Desert rose, Kudu	Alk, Flav, Sapo	Kalva S. <i>et al.</i> (2019).
7.	<i>Aegle marmelos</i> (L.) Correa	Bel, Wood apple, Holy fruit tree	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster	Veer Babita, <i>et al.</i> (2019).
8.	<i>Agave sissalana</i> Perr.	Bans keora, Sisal	Sapo, Ster	Santos J.D.G. <i>et al.</i> (2015).
9.	<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i> L.	Dochunti, Uchunti, Appa grass, Visadodi	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster, Triter	Jadav N <i>et al.</i> (2019).
10.	<i>Alangium salvifolium</i> (L.f.) Wang.	Ans phal, Sageleaved alangium, Akola	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Triter	Ratra M. <i>et al.</i> (2105).
11.	<i>Albizia lebbeck</i> (L.) Benth.	Sirish, Frywood	Alka, Flav, Sapo	Lawan, S. A. <i>et al.</i> (2017).
12.	<i>Albizia procera</i> (Roxb.) Benth.	Sada Sirish, White siris, Koroi	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster, Triter	Wankhade, M.S. <i>et al.</i> (2015).
13.	<i>Alstonia scholaris</i> (L.) R.Br.	Chatim, Devil tree, Chitvan	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster	Mistry Dhruvi, <i>et al.</i> (2016).
14.	<i>Ammannia baccifera</i> L.	Banmarich, Blistering ammania, Dadmari,	Alka, Flav, Sapo	Aiyalu Rajasekaran, <i>et al.</i> (2011).
15.	<i>Amorphophallus campanulatus</i> Blume. ex. Decne.	Mancachu, ole	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster	Firdouse S. <i>et al.</i> (2011).
16.	<i>Anacardium occidentale</i> L.	Kaju badam, Cashew nut	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster	Bastos T M, <i>et al.</i> (2019).
17.	<i>Argemone mexicana</i> L.	Seal kanta, Satyanashi, Mexican poppy	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Triter	Hossain, Md Faruq, <i>et al.</i> (2012).
18.	<i>Azadirachta indica</i> A. Juss.	Nim, Nimbay	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster	Ramadass N, <i>et al.</i> (2018).
19.	<i>Barringtonia acutangula</i> (L.)Gaertn.	Hijal, Nichul, Indian oak	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster	Arumugam Kathirvel, <i>et al.</i> (2012).
20.	<i>Butea monosperma</i> (Lam.) Taub.	Palash, Dhak, Flame of the forest	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster	Padghan Santosh V. (2018).
21.	<i>Calophyllum inophyllum</i> L.	Kathchampa, Sultan champa, Indian laurel	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster	Umamageswari K. (2017).
22.	<i>Calotropis procera</i> Aiton	Akanda	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster, Triter	Moustafa A M Y. <i>et al.</i> (2010).
23.	<i>Careya arborea</i> Roxb.	Kamber, Kumbi, Pilu	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster, Triter	Matte R. S. <i>et al.</i> (2015).
24.	<i>Carica papaya</i> (L.)	Penpe, Papaya, Papita	Alka, Flav, Sapo	Alorkpa Esther Jemima, <i>et al.</i> (2016).
25.	<i>Cascabela thevetia</i> (L.) H. Lippold	Kalke, Peeli kaner, Yellow oleander	Alka, Flav, Sapo	S Seetharaman <i>et al</i> (2017).
26.	<i>Cassia fistula</i> L.	Bandarlathi, Amaltash, Indian laburnum	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster	Bargah Rohit Kumar, <i>et al.</i> (2017).
27.	<i>Centella asiatica</i> L.(Urb.)	Thankuni, Brahma manduki, Spadeleaf	Flav, Sapo, Ster, Triter	Roy, Arpita, <i>et al.</i> (2018).
28.	<i>Cestrum nocturnum</i> L.	Hasnu hana, Rat ki rani, Night bloom jasmine	Alka, Flav, Sapo	Tyagi, Chandra, <i>et al.</i> (2017).
29.	<i>Chromolaena odorata</i> (L.)R.M. King &H. Rob.	Siam weed, devil weed	Alk, Flav, Sapo, Ster, Triter	Odutayo, Foluke Odunlami, <i>et al.</i> (2017).

30.	<i>Chrozophora rottleri</i> (Geiseler) A.Juss. ex Spreng.	Suryavarti	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Triter	Narmadaa, T., <i>et al.</i> (2012).
31.	<i>Cleistanthus collinus</i> (Roxb.) Benth.ex Hook.f.	Parasi, Garari	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster, Triter	Thamburaj, Suman, <i>et al.</i> (2013).
32.	<i>Clerodendrum infortunatum</i> L.	Ghentu, Bhand, Hill glory bower	Alka, Sapo, Ster, Triter	Hazarika, Animesh, <i>et al.</i> (2017).
33.	<i>Costus speciosus</i> (J. Koenig) Sm.	Kemuk, Kend	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster	Khayyat, Suzan, <i>et al.</i> (2017).
34.	<i>Crinum asiaticum</i> (L.)	Nagdal, Nagdan, Spiderlily, Ban lily	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster	Pittu, Vishnu, <i>et al.</i> (2018)
35.	<i>Crotalaria spp</i>	Shon, Ban sutra	Alka, Flav, Sapo	Soni Balram,. (2014).
36.	<i>Cuscuta reflexa</i> Roxb.	Swarnalata, Amar bel	Flav, Sapo, Ster, Triter	Gautam, Tapsya, <i>et al.</i> (2015).
37.	<i>Datura metel</i> L.	Dhutura	Flav, Sapo, Ster, Triter	Muthusamy Anitha, <i>et al.</i> (2014).
38.	<i>Dioscorea esculenta</i> (Lour.) Burkill	Kanta alu, Indiatic yam	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster	Salunke Chetana Anand, <i>et al.</i> (2018).
39.	<i>Diospyros melanoxylon</i> Roxb.	Kendu, Malabar ebony	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster	Janapati, Yasodha. (2012).
40.	<i>Entada scandens</i> (L.) Benth.	Gila, queensland bean	Alka, Flav, Sapo	Dey Sk. <i>et al.</i> (2013).
41.	<i>Erythrina suberosa</i> Roxb.	Palte madar/piri, Pangra	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Triter	Ahmed, Zubair, <i>et al.</i> (2020).
42.	<i>Euphorbia neriifolia</i> (L.)	Manasa sij, Patton ki send	Flav, Sapo, Triter	Swamy, Mallappa, <i>et al.</i> (2012).
43.	<i>Euphorbia tirucalli</i> L.	Lanka sij, Milk bush	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster	Sultan S, <i>et al.</i> (2016).
44.	<i>Euphorbia antiquorum</i> L.	Bajbaran, Tiktasij, Tridhara	Alka, Flav, Sapo,	Besagas, Ronnie, <i>et al.</i> (2018)
45.	<i>Euphorbia hirta</i> (L.)	Dudhilata/ bara dudhe, Barokarni, Asthema herb	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster, Triter	Asha S., <i>et al.</i> (2015).
46.	<i>Euphorbia pulcherrima</i> Willd. Ex Klotzsch	Lalpata	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster, Triter	Rauf Abdur, <i>et al.</i> (2013).
47.	<i>Gloriosa superba</i> L.	Ulat chandal/bishalanguli, Agnisikha,	Alka, , Flav, Sapo, Triter	Thirumal, Sivakumar, <i>et al.</i> (2019).
48.	<i>Grewia asiatica</i> L.	Phalsa	Flav, Sapo, Ster, Triter	Khanal Dharma Prasad, <i>et al.</i> (2016).
49.	<i>Guilandina bonduc</i> L.	Jangli bean, Kat karanj, Fever nut	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster	Mehra Bhavana, <i>et al.</i> (2015).
50.	<i>Haldinia cordifolia</i> (Roxb.) Ridsdale	Haldu, Kelkadam, Yellow teak	Alka, Flav, Sapo	Prakash Ved, <i>et al.</i> (2015).
51.	<i>Holarrhena pubescens</i> Wall. Ex G.Don	Kurchi/ Indra jab, Kutaja, Ivory tree	Alka, Flav, Ster, Triter	Saha Santanu, <i>et al.</i> (2019).
52.	<i>Holoptelea integrifolia</i> Planch.	Nata karaja, chilbil, badam tree, jungle corck tree,	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster, Triter	Kumar, Suman, <i>et al.</i> (2013).
53.	<i>Ipomoea carnea</i> Jacq.	Bara kalmi, Behaya	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Triter	Mascarenhas, M. E., <i>et al.</i> (2017).
54.	<i>Jatropha curcas</i> L.	Sada veranda, Bag veranda, Physic nut,	Alka, Flav, Sapo	Oyama, Mashanty, <i>et al.</i> (2016).
55.	<i>Jatropha gossypifolia</i> L.	Lal veranda, Ratanjoti, Cotton leaf	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster, Triter	Seth Ruchi <i>et al.</i> (2010), Saini Vijayta, <i>et al.</i> (2015).
56.	<i>Juglans regia</i> L.	Walnut	Alka, Flav, Sapo	Thakur NirmlaDevi, <i>et al.</i> (2011).
57.	<i>Justicia adhatoda</i> L.	Basak. Bakas	Alka, Sapo, Ster, Triter	Gupta Abhishek, <i>et al.</i> (2014).
58.	<i>Lantana camara</i> L.	Vut vairabi/sebani lata, Raimuniya, Lantana	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster	Raj, Sushma. (2017).
59.	<i>Lathyrus sativus</i> L.	Grass peaJangli matar,	Alka, Flav,	Al-Snafi, Ali. (2019).

60.	<i>Ludwigia perennis</i> L. Ref	Ban labanga,	Alka, Flav, Ster	Giri R. S. <i>et al.</i> (2015).
61.	<i>Madhuca longifolia</i> (J.Konig) J.F. Macbr.	Mahul, Mahua, Mowra butter tree	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster, Triter	Annalakshmi, R. <i>et al.</i> (2012).
62.	<i>Martynia annua</i> L.	Bagh nakh, Hatha-jori, Snake's head	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Triter	Kalaichelvi, K <i>et al.</i> (2016).
63.	<i>Mimosa pudica</i> L.	Lajjabati, Chui mui, Touch me not	Alka, Flav, Rote	Mohan S.M, <i>et al.</i> (2015)
64.	<i>Moringa oleifera</i> Lam.	Sajne, Drum stick tree, Sohajna	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster, Triter	Gupta, Jaya. <i>et al.</i> (2014).
65.	<i>Nerium oleander</i> L	Karabi, Kaner, Sweet scented oleander	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster, Triter	Santhi, R. <i>et al.</i> (2011).
66.	<i>Olex scandens</i> Roxb.	Badru	Alka, Sapo, Triter	Naik, Raghavendra <i>et al.</i> (2014).
67.	<i>Persicaria orientalis</i> (L.) Spach	Panimarich, Bon kunhiar	Alka, Sapo	Ansari, Prawej <i>et al.</i> (2017)
68.	<i>Plumbago indica</i> L.	, Sadachita Chitrakmool, Fire plant	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster	Kaur Darshpreet. <i>et al.</i> (2016).
69.	<i>Plumeria rubra</i> L.	Kathgolap, Champa, Pagoda tree	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster, Triter	
70.	<i>Polygonum hydropiper</i> L.	Packurmul, Water pepper, Marshpepper	Flav, Sapo, Ster	Sharif, Shahjabeen. <i>et al.</i> (2014)
71.	<i>Pongamia pinnata</i> (L.) Pierre	Karanj, India beech tree	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster, Triter	Yadav, Rahul, <i>et al.</i> (2011), Dhandapani R. <i>et al.</i> (2008).
72.	<i>Pterocarpus marsupium</i> Roxb.	Piasal, Malabar kino, Indian kino tree.	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Triter	Subramanian, Ramya. <i>et al.</i> (2008).
73.	<i>Randia spinosa</i> (Poir.)	Maniphthal, Kshudikarhar	Alka, Flav, Sapo	Sridhar V, <i>et al.</i> (2018).
74.	<i>Rauwolfia serpentina</i> (L.) Benth. Ex Kurz.	Sarpagandha, Chandra, Snake root	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster, Triter	Ramya Devi, K. A., <i>et al.</i> (2015).
75.	<i>Ricinus communis</i> L.	Rerhi, Eranda, Krapata, Castor oil plant	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster, Triter	More, Pushpalata <i>et al.</i> (2014).
76.	<i>Sapindus mukorossi</i> Gaertn.	Reetha, Indian soap berry,	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster	Bibi George <i>et al.</i> (2014).
77.	<i>Schleichera oleosa</i> (Lour.) Oken	Kusum, Ceylon oak	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Triter	Tiwari, Neha <i>et al.</i> (2017).
78.	<i>Semecarpus anacardium</i> L.f.	Bhela, Marking nut tree	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster, Triter	
79.	<i>Senna alata</i> (L.)Roxb.	Dadmari, Prapunnad	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Triter	Karthika, Ck. <i>et al.</i> (2016).
80.	<i>Senna sopheera</i> (L.) Roxb.	Kalkasunda	Flav, Sapo	Chavan Chetan, <i>et al.</i> (2011).
81.	<i>Shorea robusta</i> Gaertn.	Sal	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster, Triter	Marandi RR, <i>et al.</i> (2015).
82.	<i>Solanum nigrum</i> L.	Kakmachi, Mokoi, Black night shade	Alka, Flav, Sapo	Gogoi, Pronob. (2012).
83.	<i>Strychnos nux-vomica</i> L.	Kuchila, Snake wood	Alka, Flav, Ster	Patel, Dinesh, <i>et al.</i> (2012).
84.	<i>Tamarindus indica</i> L.	Tentul, Imli, Tamarind	Alka, Flav, Sapo	Gomathi A.C. <i>et al.</i> (2018).
85.	<i>Tephrosia purpurea</i> (L.) Pers.	Ban neel, Sarphanka, Wild indigo	Alka, Flav, Ster, Triter	Rayalu, Jayasimha. <i>et al.</i> (2013).
86.	<i>Terminalia arjuna</i> (Roxb.) Wight & Arn.	Arjun, Arjuna	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster, Triter	Mandal, Shreya <i>et al.</i> (2013).
87.	<i>Terminalia bellirica</i> (Gaertn.) Roxb.	Bahera, Belliric myrobalan	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster, Triter	Jalpa Ram, <i>et al.</i> (2015)
88.	<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i> (Willd.) Miers	Lata gulancha, guduchi, Giloy, Moon creeper	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster, Triter	Kaur, G. <i>et al.</i> (2016).
89.	<i>Tridax procumbens</i> L.	Tridaksha, Targanda, Coat-button	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster	Sawant, R. <i>et al.</i> (2013).
90.	<i>Yucca</i> sp. L.	Yucca	Alka, Flav, Sapo, Ster	Sobia, A. <i>et al.</i> (2013).

Alka: Alkaloid, Flav: Flavonoid, Sapo: Saponin, Ster: Steroid, Triter: Triterpenoid, Rote: Rotenone

Graphical Representation:

Graph 1: Graphical representation of no. of plants in families

Graph 2: Graphical representation of Ecological Status

Graph 3: Graphical representation of Life cycle

Graph 4: Graphical representation of habitat

Graph 5: Graphical representation of habitat

Graph 6: Graphical representation of Chemicals

Graph 7: Graphical representation of Used parts.

Discussions: From this survey 90 no of plant species belonging to 81 no of Genus and 46 no of families have been identified as piscicidal plants in Paschim Medinipur district. Most of the piscicidal plants are common, perennial, terrestrial and prefers to grow in wild condition represented graphically in Graph 2, 3, 4. In respect of family most of the plants are under Fabaceae followed by Euphorbiaceae and Asteraceae and has been represented in Graph-1. Among the parts used as piscicide leaves are in highest position represented in Graph 7. In respect of phytochemicals most of the plant contain saponin and flavonoid, represented in Graph 6. From Graph-5 Herbs, Shrubs and Trees are in equal numbers which contain

piscicidal chemical components. Again in respect of ecological status, most plants are common and found to grow in wild condition and some are locally threatened. So we should preserve these plants in their natural condition and become easily available to local fisherman as an alternative of harmful chemicals. It is important to note that, these piscicidal plants have more important medicinal values also. Thus the plants have potential use in medicines, agriculture and industry. After analysis, if any such compound is obtained could be commercially exploited in sustainable manner to improve the socioeconomic condition of the locals. The present study provides only preliminary report and leaves

room for further scientific and analytic research to evaluate the validity of the toxic as well as safe properties of these plants.

Conclusion: The present study aims to document the ethnobotanical knowledge of Santal and Lodha tribe of Paschim Medinipur district on fishing. These tribes have rich ethnobotanical knowledge of using plants in fishing. These plant/ plant products stupefied or killed fishes. Though it is a preliminary report, but extensive study is going on in our laboratory under the financial assistance of DSTBT, West Bengal. These studies will scientifically confirm the toxic property of these plants. As plant toxins have an impact on the wider aquatic environment, so precaution should be taken by using limited doses of plant products in a restricted area. This data regarding poisonous plants may be fruitful in developing an eco-friendly method to protect fishes from the aquaculture ponds without using any hazardous chemicals. Many more ethnobotanical piscicidal plants are yet to be reinvestigated with proper fish species and bioassay method in laboratory to verify their biocidal potential and poisonous phytochemicals. There is a huge scope for the researcher to study on piscicidal plants. Threats to biodiversity are a common feature in the last few decades. The above- mentioned plants are also not escape from various threats both anthropogenic and natural. Related government departments and NGOs should joined hand to give public awareness of the importance of diversified biodiversity, conservation of traditional indigenous knowledge on one hand and sustainable utilization of these bio-resources on other hand to improve the socio- economic condition of the locals.

Acknowledgements: The authors would like to acknowledge the support of the West Bengal Government through the Dept. Of Science and Technology and Biotechnology, Kolkata for financial assistance (Memo no. 329(Sanc.)-ST/P/S&T/17G-11/2018) in conducting this research work. We are also thankful to Dr. Gopal Chandra Bera, Principal, Midnapore College (Autonomous) for providing facility.

Reference:

- [1] Agharkar, S. P. (1991). Medicinal plants of Bombay presidency Pbl, *Scientific Publishers, Jodhpur*, 194-196.
- [2] Ahmed, Z., Aziz, S., Hanif, M., Mohiuddin, S. G., Khan, S. H. A., Ahmed, R., Ghadzi, S. M. S., Bitar, A. N. (2020). Phytochemical Screening and Enzymatic and Antioxidant Activities of *Erythrina suberosa* (Roxb.) Bark. *Journal of Pharmacy & Bioallied*

Sciences. 12(2): 192-200
DOI:10.4103/jpbs.JPBS_222_19.

- [3] Rajasekaran, A., Sivakumarll, V., Darlinquine, S. (2011). Evaluation of wound healing activity of *Ammannia baccifera* and *Blepharis maderaspatensis* leaf extracts on rats. *Rev.bras.farmacogn.*22(2): 418-427
DOI:10.1590/s0102-695x2011005000207
- [4] Alorkpa, E. J., Boadi, N. O., Badu, M., Saah, S. A. (2016). Phytochemical screening, antimicrobial and antioxidant properties of assorted *Carica papaya* leaves in Ghana. *Journal of Medicinal Plants Studies*; 4(6): 193-198.
- [5] Al-Snafi, Ali. (2019). Chemical Constituents and Pharmacological Effects of *Lathyrus Sativus*- A Review. 11(6) 1-10, DOI:10.22159/ijcpr.2019v11i6.36338.
- [6] Ambasta, S.P. (1986). The useful plants of India, CSIR New Delhi pp918, Published and printed by National Institute of Science and communication and information resource. 110012. 5th reprint.
- [7] Annalakshmi, R., Uma, R., Chandran G. S., Sahayam C. S., Charles A.(2012). Evaluation of physicochemical constants and phytochemical analysis of *Madhuca longifolia*. *Int J Nat Prod Res.* 1.(3).64-66.
- [8] Ansari, P., Josim Uddin, Md., Akther S., Azam S., Mahmud Md. K., Azad S, B., Ullah A., Hannan J. M. A.(2017). Investigation of antinociceptive activity of methanolic extract of *Persicaria orientalis* leaves in rodents. *Journal of basic and clinical physiology and pharmacology.* 28(2). 171-179. 10.1515/jbcpp-2016-0018.
- [9] Arumugam Kathirvel and Venugopal Sujatha. (2012). Phytochemical analysis and antioxidant activity of *Barringtonia acutangula* (L.) Gaertn. Leaves. *Int J Pharm Pharm Sci.* 4. (2). 277-281.
- [10] Asha, Sivaji. (2015). Phytochemical screening of *Euphorbia hirta* linn leaf extracts. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences.*3(6); 1104-1112
- [11] Ashraf M., Ayub, M., Sajjad, T., Elahi N., Ali, I., Ahmed Z. (2010). Replacement of rotenone by locally grown herbal extracts. *Int. J. Agric. Biol.* 12: 77-80
- [12] Ayotunde E.O., Offem, B., Ada, F. B. (2011). Toxicity of *Carica papaya* Linn:

- Haematological and Piscicidal effect on adult Catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*). *Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Science* 6(3):291-308.
- [13] Ayyanar M. and Tgnacimuthu S. (2010). Plants used for non-medicinal purposes by the tribal people in Kalakad Mundan thura Tiger Reserve, Southern India. *Indian J. Traditional Knowledge* 9(3): 515-518
- [14] Nagaraju, B., Ramu, A., Vidyadhara, S., ArunaKumar, Ch., Sandeep, D., Venkateswara rao B. (2016). Evaluation of in-vivo anti-diarrheal and cytotoxic activity of ethanolic extract of *Alstonia scholaris* leaves. *Int.J. Pharmaceut. Sci Rev. Res.* 41(1): 38-42
- [15] Bargah Rohit Kumar and Kushwaha Pradeep Kumar. (2017). Extraction, phytochemical screening and in-vitro antioxidant activity of *Cassia fistula* extracts. *IJRPC.* 7(4). 518-524
- [16] Bastos T M., Russo, H. M. Moretti, N. S., Schenkman, S., Marcourt, L., Gupta, M. P., Wolfender, J. L., Queiroz, E. F., Soares, M. B. P. (2019). Chemical constituents of *Anacardium occidentale* as inhibitors of *Trypanosoma cruzi* Sirtuins. *Molecules.*24.1299.
- [17] Bennet, S.S.R, (1987) Name Changes in flowering plants of India and adjacent Regions, Triseas Publishers, Dehra Dun.
- [18] Besagas, Ronnie and Gapuz, Marie. (2018). Phytochemical profiles and antioxidant activities of leaf extracts of *Euphorbia* species. *Journal of Biodiversity and Environmental Sciences.* 12.(4).59-65.
- [19] Bhagya B and KR Sridhar. (2009). Ethnobiology of coastal sand dune legumes of Southwest coast of India. *Indian J.Traditional Knowledge.* 8.(4). 611-620
- [20] Bhattacharya, S.and Chiranjib Banoushadhi., (1976-93). Ananda Publishers Pvt. Ltd., Kolkata-9. Vols. I-XI.
- [21] Bibi George and S.Shanmugam. (2014). Phytochemical screening and antimicrobial activity of fruit extract of *Sapindus mukorossi*. *Int.J.Curr.Microbiol.App.Sci:* 3.(10). 604-611
- [22] Census 2011 Data- censusindia.gov.in. retrieved on 30.4.2022.
- [23] Chadwick D J and Marsh J, (1994)Ethnobotany and the Search for New Drugs, John Wiley and Sons, Chichester, UK.
- [24] Chakroff M. (1976). Fresh water fish pond culture and management. Volunteers in Technical Assistance, Vita Publications, USA.
- [25] Chatterjee, A., and Pakrasi, S.C. (Eds), (1991-2001). The Treatise of Indian Medicinal Plants, National Institute of Science Communication, CSIR, New Delhi Vols. I-VI.
- [26] Chavan, C., Nagore, D., Todkar, S., Bhagwat D., Singh, K.(2011). Pharmacognostical and preliminary phytochemical studies of *Cassia sophera* Linn. *IJRFE.* 2.(2). 615-620.
- [27] Chiotha, S. S., Seyani, J. H., Fabiano, E. C. (1991). Molluscicidal and Piscicidal properties of indigenous plants.ICLARM Conference Proceedings (Piliines).no. 27.
- [28] Chopra, R. N., and Chopra, I.C. (1994). Indigenous Drugs of India Academic Publishers, 818508680X, 9788185086804 2ed
- [29] Chopra, R.N.(1958). Chopra's Indigenous Drugs of India. 2nd (edn.), U.N.Dhur and Sons, Calcutta.
- [30] Chopra, R.N., Nayar, S. L., Chopra, I. C., Asolkar, L. V., Kakkar, K. K. (1956). Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants, Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi.
- [31] Chopra, R.N., Nayar, S. L., Chopra, I. C., Asolkar, L. V., Kakkar, K. K. (1969). Supplement Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants, Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi.
- [32] Choudhary, R. K., Oh, S., Lee, J.(2011). An ethnomedicinal inventory of knotweeds of Indian Himalaya. *J. Med. Plants Res.* 5.(10). 2095-2103
- [33] Colonel, B., et al. (1955). Indian council of medical research. New Delhi. A review of work on Indian medicinal plants, Ed.1.
- [34] Dalela, R.C., Bhatnagar, M. C., Tyagi, A. K., Verma, S. R.(1978).Adenosine triphosphatase activity in few tissues of a fresh water teleost, *Channa gachua* following in vivo exposure to endosulfan. *Toxicology.* 11.(4).361-368.
- [35] Das, S., Dash, S. K., Padhy, S. (2003). Ethnomedicinal Information from Orissa State, India, *A Review J.Hum. Ecol.* 14(3): 165-227
- [36] Das, S.K., Mondal B., Biswas, B., Mandal A. 2018. Herbal Piscicides in Inland

- Aquaculture-A Review. *J Ecol & Nat Resources*.2.(3).000133, ISSN: 2578-4994
- [37] Dey, A., and Mukherjee A.(2015). *Plumeria rubra* L. (Apocynaceae): Ethnobotany, Phytochemistry and Pharmacology: A Mini Review. *Journal of Plant Sciences* 10. (2). 54-62
- [38] Dey, S.k., Hira, A., Ahmed, A., Howlader, Md. S. I., Khatun, A., Rahman, M., Siraj, Md. A. (2013). Phytochemical Screening and Pharmacological Activities of *Entada Scandens* seeds. *IJARNP*. 6.(1), 20-26.
- [39] Dhandapani, R. and Sabna, B. (2008). Phytochemical constituents of some Indian medicinal plants. *Anc Sci Life*.Vol: No. XXVII (4)
- [40] District Census 2011, Census 2011.co.in.2011. Retrieved 30 April 2022.
- [41] Dominic, R. and Rananujam, S.N.(2012). Traditional knowledge and ethnobotanical uses of piscicidal plants of Nagaland, North east India, *IJNPR*.3(4), 582-588.
- [42] Ekpendu, E.A., Saliu, J.K., Otitolaju, A. A. (2014). A Checklist of botanical piscicides available in Nigeria, *Open Journal of Ecology*. 4(7): 346-353.
- [43] ENVIS Centre, Manipur. (2017). ENVIS Centre, Manipur (2017). List of poisonous plants http://www.manenvis.nic.in/Database/PoisonousPlants_2935.aspx. [Accessed 16 May 2017].
- [44] Fafioye, O.O.(2005). Plants with Piscicidal Activities in Southwestern Nigeria. *Turkish Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences*. 5.91-97
- [45] Ferdous, Z., Sakil Rana, K.M., Habib, M.A.B.(2018). Piscicidal effects of plant seed extracts on predatory fish, *Channa punctatus* (Teleostei:Channidae) reared in aquarium. *Journal of Entomology and Zoology Studies*.6.(4). 1232-1236
- [46] Firdouse S and Alam Petra (2011). Phytochemical investigation of extract of *Amorphophallus campanulatus* tuber. *IJP*.3(1).32-35.
- [47] Gautam, T., Gautam, S., Keservani, R. K., Sharma, A. K.(2015). Phytochemical Screening and Wound Healing Potential of *Cuscuta reflexa*. *Journal of Chinese Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 24.(5). 292-302. 10.5246/jcps.2015.05.038.
- [48] Giri, R. S. and Dhanalakshmi, S. (2015). Phytochemical studies on biodiversity of some weeds in paddy ecosystem. Pelagia Research Library. *European Journal of Experimental Biology*. 5.(1).5-7
- [49] Gogoi, P. (2012). Phytochemical Screening of *Solanum nigrum* L and *S. myriacanthus* Dunal from Districts of Upper Assam, India. *IOSR Journal of Pharmacy (IOSRPHR)*. 2.(3). 455-459. 10.9790/3013-0230455459.
- [50] Gomathi, A.C., Xavier, R., Sadiq, A. M. (2017). Phytochemical screening of aqueous extract of Tamarind (*Tamarindus indica* L.) Shell. *International journal of basic and applied research*. 7.(11).65-69
- [51] Gupta, A., Joshi, A., Joshi, V. K.(2014). Pharmacognostical Study of *Justicia adhatoda* Linn. Leaf. *International Journal of Herbal Medicine*. 1.(6), Part A.1-4.
- [52] Gupta, J., Gupta, A., Gupta A. K.(2014). Preliminary phytochemical screening of leaves of *Moringa oleifera* Lam.J. *Chemtracks*.16.(1). 285-288.
- [53] Hazarika, R., Das, P., Baruah, C.(2015). Effect of *Ipomea Carnea* (JACQ) Leaf Extract on the Brain Tissue of *Heteropneustes Fossilis*. *Int. Res. J. Environ. Sci*. 4.(4). 22-25.
- [54] Hazarika, A. and Saha, D. (2017). Preliminary phytochemical screening and evaluation of anti-diarrhoeal activity of ethanolic extract of leaves of *Clerodendrum infortunatum*. *IJCPR*. 9.(4).143-146. 10.22159/ijcpr.2017v9i4.20980.
- [55] Kamalkishor, H. N. and Kulkarni, i K.M. (2009). Fish stupefying plants used by the Gond tribal of Mendha village of central India. *Indian J. Traditional Knowledge*. 8(4): 531-534.
- [56] Apu, A. S., Al-Baizyd, A. H., Ara, F., Bhuyan, S. H., Matin, M., Hossain, Md. F., (2012). Phytochemical analysis and bioactivities of *Argemone mexicana* Linn. *Pharmacologyonline*. 3.16-23.
- [57] <https://www.mapsofindia.com/maps/westbengal/westbengal-district.htm> (received on 01.08.2020)
- [58] Hussain, A. Z. and Kumaresan, S. (2014). Phytochemical and antimicrobial evaluation

- of *Abrus precatorius* L. *Asian Journal of Plant Science and Research*. 4.(5).10-14 [69] Jeremy, S.O.(2002). Fish poison use in Americas, <http://www.survival.com/fish.html>.
- [59] Ignacimuthu, S., Ayyanar, M., K Sivaraman, S. (2006). Ethnobotanical investigations among tribes in Madurai District of Tamil Nadu (India). *J. Ethnobiol. Ethnomed.* 2, 25: Online [70] Joshi, P. (1986). Fish stupefying plants employed by tribal of southern Rajasthan -A probe. *Curr. Sci.* 55(14): 647-650.
- [60] Yadav, N., Ganie, S. H., Singh, B., Chhillar, A. K., Yadav, S. S. (2019). Phytochemical constituents and ethnopharmacological properties of *Ageratm conyzoides* L. *Phytotherapy Research*. 33.(9).2163-2178. [71] Kalaichelvi, K., and Dhivya, S. M. (2016). Phytochemical screening and antibacterial activity of leaf extract of *Martynia annua*, L. and *Premna latifolia*, Roxb. *Journal of medicinal plant studies*. 4.(4). 84-87.
- [61] Jain, S. K. and Mudgal, A. (1999). A Handbook of Ethnobotany, Scientific Publishers, Jodhpur. [72] Kalva, S. and Raghunandan, N. (2019). Preliminary phytochemical screening and antimicrobial activity of dried flowers of *Adenium obesum*. *Int J Curr Pharm Res*. 11.(2).34-36
- [62] Jain, S. K., and Rao, R. R. (1977). A Handbook of Herbarium methods. New Delhi: Today and Tomorrow's Printers and Publishers. [73] Kamal kishor, H.N. and Kulkarni, K.M. (2009). Fish stupefying plants used by the Gond tribal of Mendha village of Central India. *Ind J Trad Know*. 8. (4).531-534
- [63] Jain, Paras. (2014). Phytochemical screening and antifungal activity of *Semecarpus Anacardium* L. (an anti-cancer plant). *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*. 5.(5). 1884-1891. 10.13040/IJPSR.0975-8232.5(5).1884-91. [74] Kamble, M. T., Chavan, B. R., Gabriel, A., Azpeitia, T., Medhe, S. V., Jain, S., Jadav, R. R. (2014). Application of *Moringa oleifera* For Development of Sustainable and Biosecure Aquaculture. *Proceeding of International Conference of Aquaculture Indonesia (ICAI)*.86-95.
- [64] Jalpa, R., Moteriya, P., Chanda, S.(2015). Phytochemical screening and reported biological activities of some medicinal plants of Gujarat region. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*. 4.(2). 192-198 [75] Karthika, C.k. and Mohamed, K.(2016). Phytochemical analysis and evaluation of antimicrobial potential of *Senna Alata* Linn. leaves extract. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research*. 9.(2).253-257.
- [65] Janapati, Y. (2012). Pharmacognostic studies on *Diospyros*. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*. 3.(9). 3438-3443. [76] Katewa, S.S., Galav, P. K., Nag, A., Jain, A. (2008). Poisonous plants of the southern Aravalli hills of Rajasthan. *Indian J. Traditional Knowledge*. 7(2): 269-272
- [66] Jawale, C. S., Vinchurkar, A. S., Dama, L. B., Pawar, K., Dama, S. B., Saikh, Y. (2012). *Cestrum nocturnum* (L) a prospective piscicide for control of predatory fish *Channa punctatus* (Bloch.). *Trends Fisheries Res*. 1(1): 14-17. [77] Kaur, D. and Prasad, S. B. (2016). Anti-acne activity of acetone extract of *Plumbago indica* root. *Asian J Pharm Clin Res*, Vol 9. (2).285-287.
- [67] Jawale, C.S. and Dama, L.B. (2010). Hematological changes in the fresh water fish, *Cyprinus carpio* exposed to sublethal concentration of piscicidal compounds from *Cestrum* species (Family: Solanaceae). *Nat. J. Life Sci*. 7(1): 81-84. [78] Kaur, G., Prabhakar, P. K., Lal, U. M., Sutte, A. (2016). Phytochemical and Biological Analysis of *Tinospora cordifolia*. *International Journal of Toxicological and Pharmacological Research*. 8.(4). 297-305.
- [68] Jawale, C.S.(2018). Piscicidal plants in India. *Trends in Fisheries Research*. 7(2):33-45, ISSN:2319-474X(p); 2319-4758(e). [79] Khanal, D., Raut, B., Kafle, M. (2016). A Comparative Study on Phytochemical And Biological Activities of two *Grewia* Species. *JMMIHS*.2.53-60. <http://doi.org/10.3126/jmmihs.v2i0.15797>.

- [80] Khare, C.P. (2007). Indian Medicinal Plants, An Illustrated Dictionary. First Indian Reprint, Springer (India) Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi, Ed-1st. 717-718.
- [81] Khayyat, S., and Alkattan, M. O. (2017). Phytochemical screening and antimicrobial activities of *Costus speciosus* and Sea Quist. *Biomedical Research*. 28.(1). 389-393.
- [82] Kirtikar, K. R., Basu, B. D. (1935). Indian Medicinal Plants, 2nd Ed., Lalit Mohan Basu Publication, Allahabad, Vol. I-IV.
- [83] Kulkarni, D. K., Kumbhojkar, M.S., Nipunage, D.S. (1990). Note on fish stupefying plants from western Maharashtra. *Indian Forester*. 0019-4816 116 4: 331-333
- [84] Kumar A., Prasad M., Mishra D., Srivastav S. K., Srivastav A. K. (2010). Toxicity of aqueous extract of euphorbia triucalli latex on catfish, *Heteropneustes fossilis*. *Ecotoxicology Environmental Safety*. 73(7): 1671-1673.
- [85] Kumar, N. (2009). Study on Suitable Piscicide for Sustainable Aquaculture Management. M.F.Sc. Thesis. West Bengal University of Animal and Fishery Sciences. Budherhat Road, Chakgeria, Kolkata, West Bengal, India
- [86] Kumar, V. and Sikarwar, R.L.S. (2003). Plants used as Fish poison by tribals of Surguja district in Chhatrishgarh, India. *Ethnobotany*. 15.87-89.
- [87] Kumar, R.S., Venkateshwar, C., Samuel, G., Rao, S. G. (2013). Phytochemical Screening of some compounds from plant leaf extracts of *Holoptelea integrifolia* (Planch.) and *Celestrus emarginata* (Grah.) used by Gondu tribes at Adilabad District, Andhrapradesh, India. *International Journal of Engineering Science Invention*. Volume 2.(8). 65-70.
- [88] Lamba, S.S. (1970). Indian piscicidal plants. *Economic Bot*. 24.(2). 134-136
- [89] Lawan, S. A., Saleh, A., Sani, B. G., Fa'iza, A. M., Sadiya, A. Z. (2017). Preliminary phytochemical constituents and phytotoxic effect of *Albizia lebbek* (L.) Benth on *Sorghum bicolor*. *Bayero Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences*. 10.(1). 405 – 408.
- [90] Mahajan, R.T., Jawale, S.M. and Choube, S.M. (1989). Piscicidal activity of some indigenous plants in: Perspectives in Aquatic Biology, edited by Dr. R.D. Kulbe. Papyrus Publications, New Delhi.: 369-375.
- [91] Malla, B. and Chhetri, R.B. (2011). Traditional use of some ichthyotoxic plants for fish stupefying practices in kavre palan chowk district of Nepal. *Ethnobot*. 23(1&2): 70-73
- [92] Mandal, S., Patra, A., Shamanta, A., Roy, S., Mandal, A., Das Mahapatra, T., Pradhan, S., Das, K., Nandi, D. (2013). Analysis of phytochemical profile of *Terminalia arjuna* bark extract with antioxidative and antimicrobial properties. *Asian. Prac. J. Trop. Biomed*. 3(12). 960-966. DOI:10.1016/S2221-1691(13) 60186-0
- [93] Marandi, R.R., S. John Britto and Prabhat, k. Soreng (2015). Phytochemical Profiling, Antibacterial Screening and Antioxidant Properties of the Sacred Tree (*Shorea Robusta* Gaertn.) of Jharkhand. *IntJ Pharm Sci Res*. 2015; 7(7):2874-88. DOI:10.13040/IJPSR.0975-8232
- [94] Martin G J, (1995). Ethno botany- A Method Manual, Champan and Hall, London.
- [95] Mascarenhas, M. E., Mandrekar C.R., Marathe P.B., Morais L.J. (2017). Phytochemical screening of selected species from convolvulaceae. *Int J Curr Pharm Res*, Vol. 9(6): 94-97. DOI:10.22159/ijcpr.2017v9i6.23438
- [96] Matte R. S., Khonde V.S. & Kale M.C. (2015). Preliminary phytochemical analysis of *Careya arborea*. *I J R B A T*, 2 (3), 176-178
- [97] Bhavana Mehra, Maurya SK, Dwivedi K.N. (2015). Pharmacognostic evaluation of Latakaranja (*Caesalpinia bonduc* [L.] Roxb.). *International Journal of Green Pharmacy*. 9 (4). S63
- [98] Budavari Susan. (1989). The Merck Index: an encyclopedia of chemicals, drugs, and biologicals 11th ed.; Winholz, M., Ed.; Merck & Co.: Rahway, NJ; USA.
- [99] Mishra Rajni., Sharma S.C. and Alka Sharma. (2014). Plant used for stupefying fishes by Tharus of Udham sing Nagar Uttarakhand, India. *Indian J. Applied Pure Bio*. 29(1): 181-183
- [100] Mistry Dhruti, Parekh B, Meonis P. (2016). Studies on phytochemical constituents and antioxidant activity of *Alstonia scholaris*. *Int. J. of Life Sciences*. 4(4):529-538
- [101] Mohan S. Pandey B, Rao SG (2015). Phytochemical Analysis and Uses of *Mimosa*

- pudica* Linn. in Chhattisgarh. *IOSR-JESTFT*. 1(3): 01-04.
- [102] More, Pushpalata, Rathod G and Pandhure, N. (2014). Phytochemical Analysis and Antibacterial Activity in *Ricinus Communis* L. *Periodic research*. RNI No. UPBIL/2012/55438, 3(1)
- [103] Moustafa A M Y, Ahmed S.H, Nabil Z.I Hussein A.A & Omran M.A. (2010). Extraction and phytochemical investigation of *Calotropis procera*: effect of plant extracts on the activity of diverse mussels. *Pharmaceutical Biology*.48(10):1080-1190. DOI:10.3109/13880200903490513
- [104] Moyon W.A.and Singh L.A. (2017). Ichthyotoxic plants of Manipur, *Int J Fauna Biol Studies*, 4(4), 29-36.
- [105] Murthy E.N, Pattanayak C, Reddy C S, Reddy KN and Raju VS(2010). Piscicidal plants used by Gond tribe of Kawal wildlife sanctuary, Andhra Pradesh, India. *Indian Journal of Natural Products and Resources*.Vol. 1(1): 97-101.
- [106] Muthusamy Anitha, Punitha M and Beslin L.G. (2014). Phytochemical screening of *Datura metel* Linn. and its antimicrobial activity on selected human pathogens. *Int. J. Bioassays*, 3 (11), 3474-3478
- [107] Nadkarni K.M. (1996). Indian Materia medica; Dr. K.M. Nadkarni's Indian Materia medica: with ayurvedic, Unani -Tibbi, Siddha, allopathic, homopathic, naturopathic & home remedies, appendices & Indexes. 1. Popular Prakashan, Lotus press.
- [108] Naik, Raghavendra, Borkar S.D., Acharya R, Harisha C.R. Shukla VJ. (2014). Pharmacognostical and preliminary phytochemical evaluation of *Olox scandens* (Roxb.) fruit. *Universal Journal of Pharmacy*. 3 (2). 62-66.
- [109] Namsa Nima D, Mandal M, Tangiang S, Mandal S C. (2011). Ethnobotany of the Monpa ethnic group at Arunachal Pradesh, India. *J. Ethnobiol. Ethnomed*. 7, 31
- [110] Narasimhan P. Lakshmi and Sharma B. D., (1991). Botanical Survey of India. Flora of Nasik District, Flora of India, Botanical Survey of India, DF Block, Sector I, Salt Lake City, Kolkata.: 644
- [111] Narmadaa, T., Devi R R, Sivaraman S, Babu H S.(2012). Phytochemical screening of the common weed *Chrozophora rottleri* to explore the antioxidant property. *Research Journal of Pharmaceutical, Biological and Chemical Sciences*. 3(1). 593-596.
- [112] Negi KS and Kanwal KS. (2009). Plants used as fish toxins in Garhwal region of Uttarakhand Himalaya. *Indian J.Traditional Knowledge*. 8(4): 535-538
- [113] Negi, S, S., et al. (2007). Medicinal and aromatic plants, G.S. Gahlot at Shiva Offset Press 14, Old C.P, Dehradun.
- [114] Neuwinger, H.D.(1994). Fish poisoning plants in Africa, *Botanica Acta*, 107(4):263-270.
- [115] Nimachow Gibji, Tahong Taga, Hui Tag, and Oyi Dai. (2008). Linkages between Bio-Resources and Human Livelihood: A Case Study of Adi Tribes of Mirem Village, Arunachal Pradesh (India) The Initiation 2008 SUFFREC Rajiv Gandhi University, Itanagar: 183-198
- [116] Odutayo, F O., Cajethan E., Taoficat K., Daniel Aina, Grace-mensah-Agyel. (2017). Phytochemical Screening and Antimicrobial Activity of *Chromolaena odorata* Leaf Extract against Selected Microorganisms. *JAMPS*. 13 (4): 1-9. 10.9734/JAMPS/2017/33523.
- [117] Oyama, M.O, Malachi O.i., Oladejo A. A. (2016). Phytochemical Screening and Antimicrobial Activity of Leaf Extract of *Jatropha curcas*. *Journal of Advances in Medical and Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 8 (1). 1-6. 10.9734/JAMPS/2016/24146.
- [118] Padghan Santosh V. (2018). Phytochemical and Physicochemical screening of different extracts of *Butea monosperma* flowers, *Int. Res. Journal of Science & Engineering*, Special Issue A3: 161-164.
- [119] Pal, D.C, Jain S k. (1998). Tribal Medicine, 1st edition, NayaPrakash, KOLKATA.
- [120] Patel, Dinesh, Patel K, Duraiswamy B, Dhanabal S.P. (2012). Phytochemical analysis and standardization of *Strychnos nux-vomica* extract through HPTLC techniques. *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Disease*. 2. Supplement 1:S56-S60. 10.1016/S2222-1808(12)60124-8.
- [121] Patil M. V., Pawar S, Patil D.A. (2006). Ethnobotany of *Butea monosperma* (Lam.)

- Kuntze in North Maharashtra, India. *Natural Product Radiance*. 5(4): 323-325
- [122] Pawar S., Patil M.V. and Patil D.A. (2004). Fish Stupefying Plants used by Tribals of North Maharashtra. *Ethnobot.* 16(1&2): 136-138
- [123] Pedro Acevedo- Rodriguez. (1990). The occurrence of Piscicides and stupefactants in the plant kingdom. *Adv. Econ.Bot.* 8: 1-23
- [124] Petr T. Toowoomba. (1999). Fish and Fisheries at Higher Altitudes: Asia, Issue 385 Issue 385 of FAO fisheries technical paper, Food and Agriculture Organization, Fish and fisheries at higher altitudes: Asia Food and agriculture organization of the United Nations. Queensland 4350 Australia. ISSN 0429-9345: 385
- [125] Vishnu Priya P and Srinivasa Rao A. (2017). Preliminary pharmacognostic and phytochemical screening of *Crinum asiaticum* and *Pedaliium murex*. *J.Nat.Prod.plant Resour.*, 7(1): 1-8
- [126] Pradhan Bharat K and Hemant K Badola. (2008). Ethnomedicinal plant use by Lepcha tribe of Dzongu valley, bordering Khangchend zonga Biosphere Reserve, in North Sikkim, India. *J. Ethnobiol. Ethnomed.* 22: 1-18
- [127] Prain, D., (1963). Bengal plants, , Botanical Survey of India, Kolkata, Vols.I & II, Reprinted Ed.
- [128] Prakash Ved, et al. (2015). Preliminary Phytochemical screening and Biological Activities of *Adina cardifolia*. *J Microb & Biochem Technol.* 7:1 DOI:10.4172/1948-5948.1000178
- [129] Rai Prabha, Kumar and Lalramnghinglova H. (2010). Ethnomedicinal Plant Resources of Mizoram, India: Implication of Traditional Knowledge in Health Care System. *Ethnobot. Leaflets.* 14: 274-305
- [130] Raj, Sushma. (2017). Preliminary phytochemical screening of *Lantana camara*, L., a major invasive species of Kerala, using different solvents. *Annals of Plant Sciences.* 6(11). 1794. 10.21746/aps.2017.6.11.13.
- [131] Ramadass N and Subramanian N. (2018). Study of phytochemical screening of neem (*Azadirachta indica*). *International Journal of Zoology Studies.* Volume 3(1): 209-212
- [132] Ramanayaka J.C. and N.S.B.M. Atapattu. (2006). Fish Anesthetic Properties of Some Local Plant Material. *Trop.Aгри. Res. Exten.* 9 :Online
- [133] Ramya Devi, K. A., Irene Wilsey, J. and Reginald, M. (2015). Qualitative phytochemical screening in different solvents of *Rauwolfia Serpentina* (Linn.) Benth., ex Kurz. stem. *IJDR.* 5(3): 3764-3765
- [134] Ratra M, and Gupta K. Rajesh (2015). Comprehensive review on Pharmacological profile of *Alangium salvifolium*: a medicinal plant. *Pharmaceutical and Bioscience Journal.* 3(3):22-28 DOI:10.20510/UKJPB/3/i3/89396
- [135] Rauf Abdur and Muhammad Naveed. (2013). Phytochemical and pharmacological evaluation of aerial parts of *Euphorbia pulcherrima* L. *Wudpecker Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacology.* 2(2): 15 – 20
- [136] Rayalu, D. Jayasimha, Laishram A, Naik J, Reddy S.(2013). Phytochemical analysis, TLC profiling and antimicrobial activity of *Tephrosia purpurea*. *Int. J. of Pharm.& Life Sci.* 4(2): 2375-2379.
- [137] Roy, Roy, Arpita and Krishnan, Laxmi. (2018). Qualitative and Quantitative Phytochemical Analysis of *Centella asiatica*. *Nat Prod Chem Res.* 6(4): 1-4. 10.4172/2329-6836.1000323.
- [138] Seetharaman S., Indra V., Sundar N., Geetha S. (2017). Phytochemical profiling, antibacterial activity and antioxidant otential of *Cascabela thevetia* (L.) whole plant extracts. *JPP.* 6(3):93-97.
- [139] Saha Santanu, Jyothi Divya, Nayak P. Shastry S.C. (2019). Preliminary phytochemical and antibacterial study of *Holarrhena pubescens* Buch. Ham. Leaves. *World journal of pharmacy and pharmaceutical sciences.* 8(8), 1416-1425
- [140] Saini Vijayta, (2015). Analysis of the Phytochemical Content of *Jatropha gossypifolia* L. *Chemical and Process Engineering Research.* 35.
- [141] Salunke Chetana Anand and Satpute Rajendra A.(2018). Phytochemical Screening and in vitro Antimicrobial Activity of Extracts from Tubers of Wild *Dioscorea* species. *Journal of Root Crops.* 44(1): 61-65

- [142] Santhi, R., Lakshmi G., Priyadharshini A.M., Anandaraj L. (2011). Phytochemical screening of *Nerium oleander* leaves and *Momordica charantia* leaves. *Int Res J Pharm.* 2 (1): 131-135.
- [143] Santos J.D.G., Vieira I. J. C., Braz-Filho R., Branco A., (2015). Chemicals from *Agave sisalana* biomass: Isolation and identification. *Int J Mol Sci.* 16(4):8761-8771.
- [144] Satya V. and Solanki C.M. (2010). Piscicidal plants used by Bhils in Western Madhya Pradesh. *Ethnobotany* 22, 1&2: 132-135
- [145] Sawant, R and Godghate, A. (2013). Preliminary phytochemical analysis of leaves of *Tridax procumbens* Linn. *International Journal of Science Environment and Technology.* 2(3). 388-394.
- [146] Seth Ruchi and Renu S. (2010). Analysis of the Phytochemical Content and Antimicrobial Activity of *Jatropha gossypifolia* L. *Archives of Applied Science Research,* 2 (5):285-291
- [147] Shahjabeen Sharif, .Tanjida A., Haque Md. Aminul., Bhujyan M.A., Shahriar Mohammad (2014). Phytochemical Screenings, Thrombolytic Activity, Membrane Stabilizing Activity and Cytotoxic Properties of *Polygonum hydropiper*. *Research Journal of Medicinal Plants,* 8 (2): 92-9810.3923/rimp.2014.9298.
- [148] Sharma S.K (1997). Addition to the fish stupefying plants employed by tribals of Southern Rajasthan. *Journal of economic and taxonomic botany.*21:249-251.
- [149] Sharma, Nidhi, Sing S., Sing S.K. (2017). Pharmacognostical standardization and preliminary phytochemical investigations on *Acacia auriculiformis* A. Cunn. Ex. Benth stem bark. *Journal of Medicinal Plants Studies.* 398 (51).
- [150] Singh D. and Singh A. (2002). Piscicidal effect of some common plants of India commonly used in freshwater bodies against target animals. *Chemosphere* 49(1): 45-49
- [151] Singh N.P. (1988). Flora of Eastern Karnataka Vol. I. *Mittal publication.*: 102-103. ISBN 817099067X, 9788170990673,
- [152] Singh S.K., .Yadahv R.P. and Singh A. (2010). Piscicidal activity of leaf and bark extract of *Thevetia peruviana* plant and their biochemical stress response on fish metabolism. *European Rev. Med. Pharmacol. Sci.* 14: 915-923
- [153] Sinha Manoj Kumar and Munshi Jayashree Datta. (2010). Eco-toxicology of Biocidal Plants Mittal Publications, 2010 - 272 pages Study conducted in Santhal Pargana, Jharkhand, India 1st ed.: 41-48
- [154] Sobia A., Muhammad Z, Rasool Nasir, Manasha Asim, Fziaa A, Munawar Iqbal, Muhammad M., and Sahid M. (2013). Antioxidant, antibacterial, antifungal activities and phytochemical analysis of dagger (*Yucca aloifolia*) leaves extracts. *Journal of Medicinal Plants.* 7. 243-249.
- [155] Sokunvary Oeung, Nov Voleak, Ung Huykhim, Roum Koemlin, Yin Voleak, Keo Samell & Chea Sin.(2017). Phytochemical analysis of different extracts of leaves of *Nicotiana tabacum* L. of Cambodia. *Asian Journal of Pharmacognosy* 1(3):18-26
- [156] Soni Balram,. (2014). Preliminary Phytochemical Screening and Antimicrobial Activity of Methanol Extract of *Crotalaria Burhia*; *PharmaTutor*; 2(9): 115-118
- [157] Sridhar V, Mamatha P., Prasad S.H. (2018). Pharmacognostical, phytochemical screening and evaluation of antioxidant activity of ethanol and aqueous extracts of *Randia spinosa* leaves. *Int J Pharm Sci & Res*; 9(11): 4854-58.
- [158] Srivastav Praven Kumar.(2014). *Achyranthus aspera*: A potent immune stimulating plant for traditional medicine. *IJPSR.*5(5):1601-1611
- [159] Stryer, L.(1995). Biochemistry, 4th ed.; W.H.Freedom & co.: New York, 544.
- [160] Subramanian, R.*et al.* (2008). Phytochemical Screening and Antibacterial Activity of Leaf Extracts of *Pterocarpus marsupium* Roxb. (Fabaceae). *Ethnobotanical Leaflets.* 12: 1029-34
- [161] Sultan, S., C. Kimaro, Ezekiel Amri. (2016). Antifungal Activity and Phytochemical Screening of Different Solvent Extracts of *Euphorbia tirucalli* Linn.. *Journal of Advances in Biology & Biotechnology.* 7(1):1-9. 10.9734/JABB/2016/26727.
- [162] Swamy, Mallappa, Neeraj Pokharen & Santosh Dahal. (2012). Phytochemical and antimicrobial studies of leaf extract of

- Euphorbia neriifolia*. *Journal of medicinal plant research*. 5(24). 5785-5788.
- [163] Tag Hui., AK Das and Pallabi Kalita. (2005). Plants used by the Hill Miri tribe of Arunachal Pradesh in ethno fisheries. *Indian J. Traditional Knowledge* 4(1): 57-64
- [164] Thakur NirmlaDevi, *et al.* (2011). Pharmacognostic and Phytochemical Investigation of *Juglans regia* Linn. Bark. *Pharmacognosy Journal*. 3.(25): 39-43.
- [165] Thamburaj, Suman and Elangomathavan, R.. (2013). Bio-prospecting of *Cleistanthus collinus* and its antibacterial activity. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research*. 6(8): 206-209.
- [166] Thirumal, Sivakumar and Duraikannu, Gajalakshmi. (2019). Phytochemical analysis and evaluation of antimicrobial activity in the whole plant extracts of *Gloriosa superba*. *AJPCR*. 12. 245-249.
- [167] Tiwari Neha and Pandey V. N.(2017). Qualitative and Quantitative Phytochemical Screening of Secondary Metabolites in Seeds of *Schleichera Oleosa* (Lour.) Oken. *IJSRSET* (3)6: 357-359
- [168] Tiwari S, and Singh A.(2003).Control of common freshwater predatory fish, *Channa punctatus*, through *Nerium indicum* leaf extracts. *Chemosphere*. 53(8):865-875.
- [169] Tiwari S. and Singh A. (2006). Biochemical stress response in freshwater fish *Channa punctatus* induced by aqueous extracts of *Euphorbia tirucalli* plant. *Chemosphere*. 64(1): 36-42
- [170] Tiwari.H.P. And A. kakkar (1990). Phytochemical examination of *Spilanthus acemella* (Murr.). *Journal of the Indian Chemical Society*.67(9).784-785.
- [171] Tyagi, Chandra, *et al.* (2017). Evaluation of anticoagulant activity of aqueous extract of *Cestrum nocturnum*. *International Journal of Phytomedicine*. 8(4). 525. 10.5138/09750185.1969.
- [172] Umamageswari K. (2017). Phytochemical screening of *Calophyllum inophyllum* Linn. *IJSRD*. Vol. 5(04) 558-560.
- [173] Vardhana Rashtra (2006). Floristic Plants of the World, Sarup and Sons, : 29
- [174] Veer Babita and Singh Ram. (2019) Phytochemical Screening and Antioxidant Activities of *Aegle marmelos* Leaves, *Analytical Chemistry Letters*, 9 (4): 478-485
- [175] Venkatachalam, Dhanapal and Thavamani, Samuel. (2018). Pharmacognostical and phytochemical evaluation of leaf of *Plumeria rubra* L. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*. Volume 7(4), 10.20959/wjpr20184-10858.
- [176] Vickery, M.L. and Vickery, B.(1981). Secondary Plant Metabolism; Macmillan Press Ltd.: London.
- [177] Wankhade, M.S. and Mulani, R. M. (2015). Chromatographic screening and phytochemical Investigation on leaf and bark methanolic extract of *Albizia procera* (Roxb.) Benth. *IJIPSR*, 3 (12), 1662-1674
- [178] Wanule D. D. and Balkhande J. V. (2012). Effect of ethanolic extract of *Ipomea carnea* leaves on guppy, *Poecilia reticulata* (peters). *Biosci. Discovery*. 3(2): 240 -242
- [179] <https://www.wikipedia.org>, Paschim Medinipur, West Bengal- (received on 16.11.2018)
- [180] Yadav Ramp P. and Singh Ajay. (2013). Toxic Effects of Two Common Euphorbiales against Freshwater Fish *Channa punctatus*. *International Journal of Traditional and Natural Medicines*, 3(2): 49-56
- [181] Yadav, Rahul, *et al.* (2011). A study on phytochemical investigation of *Pongamia Pinnata* Linn. leaves. *IJPSR*, 2(8): 2073-2079.
- [182] Yumnam J.Y. and Tripathi O.P.(2013). Ethnobotany: Plants use in fishing and hunting by Adi tribe of Arunachal Pradesh, *Indian J Tradit Know*, 12(1), 157–161.
- [183] Yunis Aj, *et al.* (2014). Acute toxicity and determination of the active constituents of aqueous extract of *Uncaria tomentosa* bark in *Hyphessobrycon eques*. *Journal of toxicology*. DOI:org/10.1155/2014/412437
- [184] Zothantluanga James H.Nagurzampuii Sailo, Arpita Paul, Ansul Shakya (2020). Pharmacognostical characterization and in vitro antioxidant activity of *Acacia pennata* (L.) Willd. leaves: A Southeast Asian medicinal plant. *Science vision*. Volume 20, issue 1, pages 16–28